

1 **Immune changes at the surface in TNBC resistance *in vitro*.**

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7 Immune changes at the surface in TNBC chemotherapy resistance *in vitro* included *Ly6K* induction,
8 activation of an Ig-like receptor known as *ISLR*, and silencing of *CD200*. IFIT family ISGs including *IFIT2*
9 were among those most significantly silenced suggesting active immune evasion through reduction of
10 senescence induced effectors at the surface.

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